

Openjournals Network and Users' Day 2026

Organized yearly by [Openjournals.nl](https://openjournals.nl) - «an online platform and support team, for publishing scholarly, peer-reviewed journals according to the diamond open access publishing model» - the Network and Users' Day aims at bringing together representatives of the openjournals.nl community and members of the general public, such as (university) librarians and (open access) policy-makers.

Following the morning programme – which included a presentation of the [OJS Open Journal Systems-software](#) (by [Kay Pepping](#)) and a guided tour of the [Trippenhuis](#), where the event was hosted – the afternoon session consisted of an introduction to the Diamond Open Access landscape in The Netherlands, given by [Jan Willem Wijnen](#) (programme manager of openjournals.nl), and of three panel discussions.

Among the topics discussed by Jan Willem Wijnen – organisations, projects, policies, journals, and the results of a recent survey (“What is out there in the Dutch DOA landscape?”, “What are the struggles?”, “How to assist DOA journals?”) – an overview of the (main) actors can be of interest to those (partly) new to Diamond Open Access:

- [Expertise Centre Diamond Open Access](#)
- [NUPs Netherlands University Presses](#) ([Delft](#), [Groningen](#), [Leiden](#), [Maastricht](#), [Nijmegen](#), [Tilburg](#))
- [Open Science NL](#)
- [SciPost](#)

The highlights from the three panel discussions (all moderated by Jan Willem Wijnen):

Panel 1: Funding DOA Journals. [Pieterbas Lalleman](#) (Fontys Hogeschool, [Tijdschrift Verpleegkunde](#)), [Margreet Nieborg](#) (University of Groningen Press) and [Jean-Sébastien Caux](#) (UvA, [SciPost](#)) gave answer to questions such as “How are DOA journals funded?”, “What expenses do they have?”, “What funding options are available?”, “Are they supported in other ways?”.

Caux stole the scene with a brilliant illustration of the (so far, successful) business model beyond *SciPost*, the online scientific publication portal he established in 2016: described in more detail on *SciPost*'s [website](#), the model shifted from the more

conventional approach of 'first the money, then the articles' to one - non-capitalistic and post-facto, according to Caux – where insuring to have scholars for high quality articles comes first, and only then follows the search for funds from potential supporters, such as libraries and universities (among which the UvA Library).

A shift – this time in the way open access university budgets are invested - was also proposed by Margreet Nieborg, who stated that if just 1% of the money the University of Groningen pays out on [R&P deals](#) were to go to its university press, the latter could smoothly support its activities. Nieborg's remark luckily seems to fit with the insights and propositions of the recent UNL's [A new open access strategy for The Netherlands](#) ("reallocating budget while maintaining cost-neutrality").

A more controversial proposal was Caux's of making researchers – those determined to publish in journals with high APCs to improve their careers - pay themselves for the fees, on the grounds that the higher salaries implied by their career's advancements would pay back the APC-expenses.

Panel 2: Peer-review and peer-reviewers. [Tessa Cramer](#) (Fontys Hogeschool), [Evelien Dera](#) (Zuyd Hogeschool), and [Djoerd Hiemstra](#) (Radboud Universiteit) tackled questions such as *“How to find more peer-reviewers and accelerate the peer-review process?”*, and *“What are the benefits of open peer-review and other peer-review methods?”*.

While this topic lies somehow farther away from libraries' primary concerns around Diamond Open Access, it was interesting to hear about (potential) issues of this publication model, such as:

- the tension between the number of articles submitted to a journal and the number of available reviewers (possibly resulting in a short-circuit in the editorial board, as mentioned by Evelien Dera for the [Tijdschrift voor Jeugdgezondheidszorg](#));
- the [open peer review](#) model and its role in increasing or just reducing the room for (openly) discriminatory practices by reviewers;
- the idea of paying peer reviewers for their work, and whether this would rather discourage them to work for non-commercial publishers with limited resources, if offered a better paid position at a big(ger) publishing corporations;

- the importance of ‘audacity’ and ‘kindness’ as ideas beyond [Futures Reframed](#), the journal Tessa Kramer co-founded with UvA’s [Roanne van Voorst](#), further mentioning Oxford professor [Charles Foster](#) as an important source of inspiration ([The deadly dangers of peer review](#));
- ‘kindness’ being mentioned again by Djoerd Heemstra ([Information Retrieval Research Journal](#)) as an important quality of reviewers’ work, i.e. inviting reviewers not to look mainly/only for ‘wrong’ stuff in an article.

Panel 3: AI and scholarly publishing. [Emmanuel Keuleers](#) (Tilburg University), [Maria Mos](#) (Tilburg University, [Dutch Journal of Applied Linguistics](#)), [Michael Nagenborg](#) (Universiteit Twente, [Journal of Human-Technology Relations](#)) and [Wouter Egelmeers](#) (KNAW, [Journal of the History of Knowledge](#) and [BMGN Low Countries Historical Review](#)) discussed questions such as “How do editorial boards deal with AI?”, “Should there be guidelines and policies?”, and “How does AI affect quality control and peer-review?”.

(Developing) policies and/or approaches to cope with how AI is affecting scholarly publishing varied from posting the details of retracted papers having used GenAI on the journal’s website (as a deterrent) to concerns about copyright infringement if copy-pasting a submitted manuscript in a GenAI tool for control.

Mildly positive opportunities – using GenAI to assist people with dyslexia – were exchanged with firm rejections, such as (when it has been assessed that GenAI was used for writing a manuscript): *“If you haven’t bothered to write, I won’t bother to read”*. The latter, by extension, becoming an opportunity to reflect on how research needs to slow down, because if researchers are stressed out it’s not a question of finding ways (GenAI-assisted) for doing more and quicker, but to assess and reform the whole system of knowledge production.